

ETHYL METHANE SULFONATE INDUCED YIELD AMPLIFICATION IN COWPEA (*Vigna unguiculata* L. Walp)

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ABSTRACT

Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*), which is a vital leguminous crop, enhances soil fertility through nitrogen fixation but suffers significant yield losses due to biotic and abiotic factors. Despite the existence of available germplasm, its genetic variability remains narrow due to self-pollination. This study investigated the potential of Ethyl Methane Sulfonate (EMS) mutagenesis to improve cowpea yield and agronomic traits. Five cowpea accessions (TVU12047, TVU17315, TVU114409, TVU17330, and TVU932) were treated with EMS concentrations (0c, 0w, 0.75%, and 1.25%) and evaluated in a screen house in a completely randomised design with three replications. Results revealed significant genotypic variation, with TVU17315 (M2) and TVU17330 (M2) mutants showing superior performance in yield components. A dose-dependent response was observed, where 0.75% EMS optimally enhanced traits such as pods per plant, seeds per pod, and 100-seed weight, while higher doses reduced germination and growth. Mutagenized lines exhibited early flowering (9–10 days earlier than controls), likely due to altered flowering gene expression. The study demonstrates that EMS mutagenesis effectively generates genetic variability, with 0.75% EMS identified as the optimal concentration for improving yield without excessive growth inhibition. These findings highlight the potential of mutation breeding in developing high-yielding varieties, addressing food security challenges in climate-vulnerable regions. Further field evaluations are recommended to validate mutant stability and adaptability.

Keywords: Cowpea, EMS mutagenesis, genetic variability, yield improvement, mutation breeding

INTRODUCTION

Cowpea is one of the most important leguminous crops grown globally, belonging to the family Fabaceae. It is believed to have originated in West and Southern Africa and is widely distributed in East and Central Africa, India, Asia, South and Central America. According to FAO (2017), the world production of cowpea is about 5.6 metric tonnes cultivated in an area

of 12.6 million hectares. Of the world's total cowpea production, Africa produced 95.3%, followed by Asia (2.8%), America (1.3%), and Europe (0.6%). The leading producers in Africa are Nigeria, Niger and Burkina Faso. Cowpea enhances the fertility of the soil by fixing atmospheric nitrogen, which leads to higher yields of nitrogen-intensive crops grown with or after it (Matusso et al., 2014).

In Sub-Saharan Africa, cowpea suffers considerable damage due to frequent terminal drought as a result of climate change, especially during the flowering and pod filling stage (Armah et al., 2011). According to Agbicodo et al. (2009), the cowpea crop exposed to moisture stress at the early flowering and pod filling stage results in losses of up to 80 per cent of yield. In spite of rich collections of germplasm available at the various national breeding institutions, cowpea genetic variability is narrow due to the self-pollinating nature of the crop. (Asare et al., 2010). In both conventional and molecular methods of plant breeding, breeders depend on the availability of sufficient levels of genetic variation for the trait of interest for crop improvement. There is a need to create genetic variation in the cowpea genotype with desired traits such as grain yield through mutation. Mutagenesis alters the genetic makeup of plants by interference and modification of genes. It is an efficient tool used to create new desirable genetic variability. Induced mutagenesis, recognised as a valuable supplement to conventional breeding in crop improvement programs, involves subjecting organisms to physical and chemical mutagens to create variations at the molecular level. One such chemical mutagen is Ethyl Methane Sulfonate (EMS), known for its efficiency in inducing genetic variability (Predieri, 2001). Therefore, this research investigates the potential of Ethyl Methane Sulfonate (EMS) mutagenesis to improve yield and other agronomic traits of cowpea.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Study Area

The experiment was carried out during the

dry season at the screen house of Kwara State University (KWASU), Malete located in the Southern Guinea Savannah agroecology of Nigeria, on an altitude of 316.37 m. a. s. l. within latitude 08°42'N to 08°43'N and longitude 04°28'2'E to 4°28'3'E of the equator. The climate is tropical with annual rainfall, maximum temperature, maximum relative humidity and a daily photoperiod of 1500 mm, 38 °C, 75 % and 7.1 hours, respectively (Olarenwaju, 2009). The experiment started in December 2023 and was terminated in February 2024 for the first and December 2024 and was terminated in February 2025 for second planting.

Treatments and Experimental Design

Five (5) cowpea accessions: TVU12047, TVU 17315, TVU114409, TVU17330 and TVU932, which were obtained at the International Institute for Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Ibadan, and four (4) EMS concentrations (0c, 0w, 0.75 and 1.25%). Each concentration had 100 seeds. Seeds were soaked in the solutions for 16 hours. After that, the chemical reaction and activity of the EMS will be terminated using sodium thiosulfate solution to neutralize and stop the reaction by inactivating the EMS. After treatment along with their respective control, they were sown in the pot to raise M1 generation in a complete randomized design (CRD) with three replications. All the surviving individual plants were harvested in each treatment in the M1 generation. M1 plants having sufficient seeds in different treatments were grown to raise M2 in the second planting. In the screen house, perforated pots of 10 liter were filled with 5 kg of sterilized topsoil. Four (4) seeds were sown per hole and later thinned to two seedlings at two weeks after planting. The

plants were irrigated as and when due to the field capacity of the pots.

Trait Evaluation and Analysis

Data were collected on the following plant parameters: Vegetative growth parameters were collected at 4 and 8 weeks after sowing, while seed yield components were collected at plant maturity: Average Plant Height (cm), Average Number of Leaflet, Average Leaflet Area (cm²), Number of seeds germinated, number of days to germination, Average Number of Pods Per Plant, Average Number of Seeds Per Pod, Number of Seeds Per Plant and 100 Seed Weight per Plant at Harvest. All data collected were summarized, computed and analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean, range, standard deviation and coefficient of variation), Analysis of variance (combined), Duncan Multiple Range Test using R statistical software.

RESULTS

Variation in growth characters of five (5) cowpea accessions induced by four (4) levels of ethyl methane sulfonate at the second planting

The mean values for ethyl methane sulfonate and accession on growth characters, which show highly significant variation shown in Table 1. Water soaking (0w) recorded least for number of days to germination and high number of seed germinated, leaf area at 8weeks after planting and number of stomata per plant.

No soaking (0_c) recorded the highest plant height at 4 and 8weeks after planting, number of leaves at 4weeks after planting. In addition, TVU17330 gave the highest

performance for number of seed germinated, plant height and leave area at 4weeks and 8weeks after planting and number of stomata per plant and

TVU12047 had least day to germination while TVU14409 (M) had highest number

of leaves at 4weeks after planting and TVU17330 (M) recorded highest for

number of leaves at 8weeks after planting. TVU932 had the lowest number of seed germinated, plant height and leave area at 4 and 8weeks after planting while,

TVU17330 (M²) has lowest for number of stomata after planting, TVU14409 recorded highest number of days to germination and leave area at 4 and 8weeks after planting, TVU12047 had lowest number of leaves at 4 weeks after planting, TVU17330 had lowest number of leaves at 8 weeks after planting.

Variation in yield components of five (5) cowpea accessions induced by four (4) levels of ethyl methane sulfonate at the second planting

Table 2 shows the mean values for ethyl methane sulfonate, water treatment and accession on yield components, which shows highly significant variation. Ethyl methane sulfonate at 0.75% recorded the highest for number of loci per pod, number pod per plant, number of seeds per plant, seed weight and least days to flowering. Meanwhile, TVU17315 gave the highest performance for number of pod per plant, number of seeds per pod, number of seeds per plant, pod length and seed weight,

while 2

TVU17315 (M) gave highest number of loci per plant and TVU17330 (M²) had least days to flowering.

levels of ethyl methane sulfonate at the second planting

Table 1: Mean values of growth characters of five (5) cowpea accessions induced by four (4)

ACCESSION	NDG	NSG	PH4	PH8	NST
					60.80ab
					45.05 c
					57.91b
					72.16 a
					45.36 c
					38.66cd
					29.55d
					11.94e
					70.77
					a
					75.11
					a
					36.23
					b
					33.00
					b

NB: The letters in ascending order a, b, c... e. t. c. indicate the level of significance in the mean table. Figures with the same letter are not significantly different. NST: Number of seeds germinated; NDG: germination %; NSG: number of seeds germinated after 4 weeks; PH4: plant height at 4 weeks; PH8: plant height at 8 weeks; NST: Number of seeds germinated; NDG: germination %; NSG: number of seeds germinated after 4 weeks; PH4: plant height at 4 weeks; PH8: plant height at 8 weeks.

Table 2: Mean values of yield components of five (5) cowpea accessions induced by four (4) levels of ethyl methane

Variety	DTF	NPD	NSP	NSTT	HSW (g)
TVU12047	54.33a	6.64bc 1.73b	5.94bc	10.08c	29.21bc
TVU17315	44.60b	10.82b 4.00a	12.15a	67.50a	48.87a
TVU17315 (M)	40.66cd	10.80b 3.15ab	6.80bc	31.20b	32.60b
TVU14409 (M)	41.77bc	9.50b	9.16ab	10.00c	17.76d
TVU17330	55.90a	6.45bc 1.66b	5.90bc	11.18c	23.47cd
TVU932	51.88a	11.45a 3.00ab	9.31ab	51.16a	43.21a
ETHYL METHANESULFONATE	38.52d	5.10bc 2.71ab	5.00c	34.80b	38.23b
0c	38.45d	5.00c	8.50bc	15.20bc	27.78bc
0w	45.55a	1.93	8.40a	13.38c	20.37
0.75%	47.57a	1.83	7.65a	14.13c	28.71
1.25%	38.95b	b	8.58a	40.41a	b
	39.56b	b	8.40a	29.00b	b
		3.21			35.05

NSP: Number of seeds per pod, HSW: Hundred seed weight, NPD: Number of pods per plant, NSTT: Number of seeds per plant, M: Mutant.

are not significantly different. Different letters indicate significant differences between treatments. Significant differences are indicated by different letters in the same column.

Mean for the interaction between accession and ethyl methane sulfonate (AxE) Table 3 shows the mean values of the yield characters for the interactions between accession and ethyl methane sulfonate. TVU12047 had least days to germination

(3.00) at no soaking (E_0) and TVU17315 has the highest plant height at 8 weeks after planting and number of seed germinated

(36.77cm and 6.11) at no soaking (E_0), while TVU17330 recorded highest number of leaves and leave area (27.21 and 43.52cm²) at water soaking (E_1),

whereas, TVU114409 recorded highest number of stomata (91.33) at no soaking (E_0) compared to other accessions.

Whereas, for the yield component TVU17330(M^2) recorded the least days to flowering, highest number of loci per plant, number of seed per pods, number of seed per plant and 100 seed weight (33.28,

13.11, 15.87, 68.00 and 49.21g respectively) at 0.75% ethyl methane sulfonate, whereas TVU17330 (M^2) had highest number of pods per plant (4.88) at 0.75% ethyl methane sulfonate compared to other accessions.

However, TVU12047 recorded highest days to germination at 1.25% ethyl methane

sulfonate (E_3), TVU17315 has least for number of seed germinated, and number of stomata and leave area 8weeks after

planting at 1.25% ethyl methane sulfonate (E_3), TVU17330(M^2) had the least for plant height 8weeks after planting and TVU932 recorded the least for number of leaves 8weeks after planting at 1.25% ethyl methane sulfonate (E_3).

Meanwhile, TVU932 recorded the least for all the yield components at 1.25% ethyl methane sulfonate (E_3) except for days to flowering, in which TVU932 had the highest at no soaking (E_0)

DISCUSSION

Genotypic variation for growth and yield components

The analysis of variance shows that the accession had significant in growth and yield components. TVU17330 gave the highest performance for number of seed germinated, plant height and leave area at 4weeks and 8weeks after planting and number of stomata per plant and

TVU12047 had least day to germination

and TVU14409 (M) had highest number of

leaves at 4weeks after planting and

TVU17330 (M) recorded highest for

number of leaves at 8weeks after planting.

Meanwhile, TVU17315 gave the highest

performance for number of pod per plant,

number of seeds per pod, number of seeds

per plant, pod length and seed weight, while

TVU17315 (M) gave highest number of

loci per plant and TVU17330 (M²) had

least days to flowering.

According to Byrne et al. (2018), genetic variability gives plants their variation.

Concurs with Giller (2001), who found that

several legumes exhibit significant genetic

diversity. Yusuf and Aliyu (2024), also

reported that there is genetic variability in

soybean

Crop improvement relies on genetic diversity of plant genetic resources. A high genetic diversity provides an opportunity for plant breeders to develop cultivars with desirable characteristics.

The presence of high yielding potential of

TVU17315, TVU17315 (M²) and TVU17330 (M)

could indicate the likelihood of trait selection based on

genotypic variation among the accessions

which includes the mutant. As a result of

heterogeneity, breeder could pick up

TVU17315, TVU17315 (M²) and

TVU17330 (M) for cowpea improvement.

Mutagenesis effect of ethyl methane sulfonate on growth and yield of cowpea

Mutation technology is used to create variation in the search of desired traits such as high yield. It is an effective technique to increase resilience to drought and yield in crops grown in drought-prone countries. Among the different present approaches, mutagenesis and mutation breeding and the isolation of improved or novel phenotypes in conjunction with conventional breeding programs can result in mutant varieties endowed with new and desirable variations

agrometrical traits. (Spreeth et al.,

2004). In the present study, all the five

accessions of cowpea produced significant

variation in growth and yield when induced

with ethyl methane sulfonate.

Many research studies have reported

mutation was used in cowpea to create

genetic diversity and improve drought

tolerance and yield productivity. Ronde and

Spreeth (2007) used mutation technology

in obtaining drought tolerant lines giving

relatively good yields under drought stress

conditions and having favourable traits.

There was significant variation in response

of cowpea to different rates of mutagen (0c,

0w, 0.75% and 1.25%) during the planting

seasons.

For the growth parameters, Water soaking

(0w) recorded the least for the number of

days to germination and highest for the

number of seed germinated, number of

leaves at 4 and 8weeks after planting. No

soaking (0c) recorded the highest for plant

height at 4 and 8weeks after planting at first

planting. While water soaking (0w)

recorded the least for the number of days to

germination, number of seeds germinated,

leave area at 8weeks after planting and

number of stomata per plant. No soaking

(0c) recorded the highest plant height at 4

and 8weeks after planting, number of

leaves at 4weeks after planting.. Whereas,

for the yield components, ethyl methane sulfonate at 0.75% recorded the highest for number of loci per pod, number of pod per plant, number of seeds per plant and seed weight. In contrast, No soaking (0c) recorded the highest for number of loci per pod and pod length, whereas 1.25% Ethyl methane sulfonate had the least days to flowering during the first planting. In comparison, Ethyl methane sulfonate at 0.75% recorded the highest for number of loci per pod, number pods per plant, number of seeds per plant, seed weight and least days to flowering. In this study, a dose- dependent reduction of germination in the mutant seeds was observed. Thus, seed germination decreases with an increase in ethyl methane sulfate (mutagen). These results are in consonance with the findings of Gnankambary et al. (2019) in cowpea and Horn (2016) in cowpea. The decrease in seed germination at a high dose may be due to mutagen-induced disturbances in the biophysical metabolic pathways that play a key role in seed germination. According to De Micco et al. (2011), the decline in seed germination after the mutagen treatment is attributed to the abnormalities induced by the mutagen in the mitotic cycles and the metabolic pathway of the cell. Studies indicate that induced mutagenesis has successfully modified several plant traits such as plant height, maturity, seed shattering resistance, disease resistance, oil quality and quantity, malting quality, size, quality of starch granules and yield of cowpea (Goyal and Khan, 2010). The grand mean value for interaction between accession and ethyl methane sulfate indicated that across the treatments there was significant variation among growth and yield component characters of mutant accession compare to untreated.

TVU12047 had least days to germination at no soaking (E_0) and TVU17315 has the highest plant height at 8 weeks after planting and number of seed germinated at no soaking (E_0), while TVU17330 recorded highest number of leaves and leave area at water soaking (E_1), whereas, TVU114409 recorded highest number of stomata at no soaking (E_0) compared to other accession. All mutant accessions generally caused a substantive decrease in the plant height, number of leaves and leave area of the cowpea accessions compared with the control treatment. The current findings show that the induced accessions significantly reduce growth parameters with an increase in ethyl methane sulfonate. Horn and Shimelis (2013) also made a similar observation that there is a progressive increase in the mean induced seedling length reduction of epicotyl and hypocotyl in cowpea genotypes as the mutagen increased. Also this mutagen dose causes a very high degree of sterility and lethality of M1 plants and therefore plant breeding programmes aimed at enhancing only one or two quantitative traits should use a dose of a mutagen causing a reduction in the growth of less than 30 percent (Szarejko et al., 2017).

TVU17330(M²) recorded the least days to flowering and highest number of loci per plant, number of seed per pods, number of seed per plant and 100 seed weight at 0.75% ethyl methane sulfonate, whereas TVU17330(M¹) had highest number of pods per plant at 0.75% ethyl methane sulfonate compared to other accessions. In this study, number of days to flowering reduced among the selected putative mutants compared to the control in the (M²) generations. Some of the putative mutants were observed to have flowered 8-9days earlier than the control. The reduction in the

number of days to flowering proves that mutagen stimulates gibberellin and brassinosteroids biosynthesis which activate the LEAFY (LFY) gene and causes the putative mutants to flowered earlier than the control. The number of loci per pod, number pod per plant, number of seeds per plant and the seed weight, increased in mutants compared to the control in the M2 generation. The Increases in the yield components after mutagenic treatment has also been reported by Horn (2016) in cowpea, Wani (2011) in chickpea and Tulmann and Alves (1997) in legumes.

Horn (2016) induced four cowpea varieties. Observed that some of the cowpea mutants recorded higher yield components. The authors found that under drought stress conditions mutant line compared best with the parent line. More studies using mutation technology for the development of drought-tolerant genotypes with improved yield in various parts of the world where drought is a challenge need to be considered. According to Hallajia (2016), mutation- assisted plant breeding will play a crucial role in the generation of “designer crop varieties” to address the challenges due to drought and the global plant-product insecurity.

CONCLUSION

The application of EMS mutagenesis successfully created valuable phenotypic variation: A dose-dependent response was observed, with 0.75% EMS concentration proving most effective for enhancing yield components such as number of loci per pod, pods per plant, seeds per plant, and 100-seed weight. Mutagenized lines

showed accelerated flowering (9-10 days earlier than controls), likely due to mutagen-induced stimulation of flowering-related genes. While higher mutagen doses reduced germination and growth parameters due to metabolic disturbances, optimal doses (0.75% EMS) and enhanced yield components in selected mutants. The breeding Implications of the study identified promising genetic material for cowpea

improvement programs: accession 2

TVU17315, TVU17315 (M) and TVU17330 (M²) demonstrated high yield potential at 0.75% EMS and could serve as valuable breeding material.

Mutagenesis inducement of 0.75% EMS treatment emerged as optimal for creating beneficial mutations without excessive growth inhibition. The early flowering in mutants through reduced days to flowering in mutagenized lines could be valuable for developing early-maturing varieties adapted to drought-prone environments. These results support the use of induced mutagenesis as a powerful tool for creating genetic variation in cowpea breeding programs, particularly for developing varieties with improved yield potential and drought tolerance. The findings contribute to ongoing efforts to enhance cowpea productivity in regions facing climate challenges and food security concerns. Future research should focus on field evaluation of these promising mutants across multiple environments to assess their stability and adaptation potential.

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